

Synthesis, Spectral and Anticarboxylesterase Properties of 3-Substituted-1,5-dihydro-7,8-dimethyl-2,4,3-benzodioxaphosphepin-3-oxides

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In continuation of our studies on the synthesis of new biologically active organophosphorus heterocyclic compounds, we undertook the preparation of benzodioxaphosphepin-3-oxides. The title compounds (1a—m) were prepared by the condensation of phosphorodichloridates with 4,5-dimethyl-1,2-benzenedimethanol in dry tetrahydrofuran in the presence of triethylamine. On the other hand, the preparation of 3-substituted-1,5-dihydro-7,8-dimethyl-2,4,3-benzodioxaphosphepin-3-oxides (2a—e) were achieved in two steps, through the intermediate monochloride, 3-chloro-1,5-dihydro-7,8-dimethyl-2,4,3-benzodioxaphosphepin-3-oxides (1; R = Cl), the preparation of which was accomplished by the treatment of phosphorusoxychloride with 4,5-dimethyl-1,2-dihydroxymethyl in the presence of triethylamine. The monochloride (1; R = Cl) thus obtained was treated *in situ* with respective nucleophiles to get 2a—e.

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| 1a; R = C ₆ H ₅ | 1h; R = 2,5-(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ O |
| 1b; R = C ₆ H ₄ O | 1i; R = 2,6-(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ O |
| 1c; R = 2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ O | 1j; R = 3,4-(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ O |
| 1d; R = 4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ O | 1k; R = 3,5-(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ O |
| 1e; R = 2-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ O | 1l; R = 4-Cl-3-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃ O |
| 1f; R = 3-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ O | 1m; R = 2,4-Cl ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ O |
| 1g; R = 4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ O | |
| 2a; R = Piperazine | 2d; R = 4-Chlorothiophenol |
| 2b; R = Dicyclohexylamine | 2e; R = <i>N</i> -Methylaniline |
| 2c; R = 8-Hydroxyquinoline | |

Ir spectra of 1a—m and 2a—e showed medium to strong bands¹ in the regions 1 320—1 300, 1 320—1 260 (P=O), 1 190—1 130, 1 240—1 160 (P—O—C aryl), 1 190—1 130 and 1 200—1 100 (P—O—C aliphatic). In ¹H nmr spectra, methylene protons displaying six-line signal is contrary to the expected eight-line AB part of ABX pattern X being phosphorus². The methylene proton of 2a—e appeared as multiplets due to coupling between phosphorus and methylene protons. The ¹³C nmr spectra (δ ppm) exhibited³

signals for C-10, C-11, C-6, C-9, C-7, C-8, C-1 and C-5 in the regions δ 132.18—133.85, 130.24—131.9, 136.28—137.98 and 66.94—69.23 (²J_{POC-1,C-5}, 0—7.0 Hz). The two methyl carbons resonated as a singlet at 19.17—19.29. The ¹³C nmr shifts of phenoxy moiety resonated in the expected range, and the signals for piperazine moiety appeared at δ 45.75 and 44.15 for C-2, C-6 and C-3, C-5. *p*-Chlorothiophenol moiety exhibited signals for C-1, C-2, C-6, and C-7, C-5 at δ 132.13, 131.34—128.93. The signal for C-4 was observed at δ 135.04.

The compounds (1d, g, h, l, m and 2a—e) were screened *in vitro* for anticholinesterase activity by the colorimetric technique⁴, using sheep liver as the source for the enzyme, α-naphthyl acetate as substrate and Fast Blue B (a diazonium salt) as the colouring agent. The results obtained were compared with the inhibitory effect at concentrations 5, 10 and 20 ppm of standard commercial pesticide-methyl parathion (Technical grade).

Experimental

All the melting points were determined on a Mel-temp apparatus and are uncorrected. Their spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian HA 100 spectrometer (100 MHz), ¹³C nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a NT 360 WB spectrometer (90.50 MHz) with tetramethylsilane as an internal standard and mass spectra on a Krates MS-80 spectrometer (70 eV) at a resolution of 10000. The elemental analyses were performed at Regional Sophisticated Instrumentation Centre, Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow.

4,5-Dimethyl-1,2-benzenedimethanol and phenylphosphorodichloridates were prepared as described in literature.

3-Phenoxy-1,5-dihydro-7,8-dimethyl-2,4,3-benzodioxaphosphepin-3-oxide (1b): Phenylphosphorodichloridate (1.05 g, 0.005 mol) in dry benzene (20 ml) was added to a stirred mixture of 4,5-dimethyl-1,2-benzenedimethanol (0.83 g, 0.005 mol) and triethylamine (1.01 g, 0.01 mol) in tetrahydrofuran (20 ml). The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 2 h and for another 2 h at 50—60°. The progress of

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NOTES

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS (1a—m, 2a—e)*				
Compd.* no.	M.p. °C	¹ Hnmr δ, J(Hz)	¹³ C nmr δ, J(Hz)	m/z (%)
1a	120—21	2.33 (6H, s, 2CH ₃), 5.02 (Ha), 5.30 (Hb), J (HaHb) 13.3, J _p (Ha), 9.3, J _p (Hb) 10.2, 7.0—7.36 (7H, m, arom)	—	—
b	146—47	2.27 (6H, s, 2CH ₃), 5.03 (Ha), 5.29 (Hb), J (HaHb) 13.2, J _p (Ha) 10.1, J _p (Hb) 11.0, 7.07—7.35 (7H, m, arom)	—	—
c	83—90	2.25 (6H, s, 2CH ₃), 5.03 (Ha), 5.30 (Hb), J (HaHb) 13.1, J _p (Ha) 10.2, J _p (Hb) 12.5, 7.0—7.36 (6H, m, arom)	—	—
d	126—27	2.26 (6H, s, 2CH ₃), 5.10(Ha), 5.26 (Hb), J (HaHb) 13.2, J _p (Ha) 10.1, J _p (Hb) 12.6, 7.0—7.36 (6H, m, arom)	—	—
e	110—12	2.34 (6H, s, 2CH ₃), 5.18 (Ha), 5.28 (Hb), J (HaHb) 13.4, J _p (Ha) 9.2, J _p (Hb) 10.5, 7.0—7.37 (6H, m, arom)	—	318(22), 302(10), 220(8), 205(7), 181(15), 132(100), 117(12), 91(13), 77(8)
f	141—43	2.27 (6H, s, 2CH ₃), 5.10 (Ha), 5.32 (Hb), J (HaHb) 13.3, J _p (Ha) 10.2, J _p (Hb) 10.3, 7.07—7.34 (6H, m, arom)	68.83 (d, J 7.0), 130.44, 137.71, 132.39, 19.22, 150.20 (d, J 5.6), 120.20 (d, J 5.1), 140.1, 125.84, 129.41, 116.9, 21.21	318(12), 303(22), 288(36), 211(15), 181(100), 132(47), 91(5)
g	145—47	2.27 (6H, s, 2CH ₃), 5.10 (Ha), 5.26 (Hb), J (HaHb) 13.2, J _p (Ha) 10.0, J _p (Hb) 11.6, 7.18—7.26 (6H, m, arom), 2.33 (3H, s, CH ₃)	—	318(14), 303(22), 288(27), 181(91), 132(100), 91(54), 77(26)
h	134—35	2.27 (6H, s, 2CH ₃), 5.07 (Ha), 5.30 (Hb), J (HaHb) 13.0, J _p (Ha) 10.3, J _p (Hb) 12.4, 7.06—7.25 (6H, m, arom), 2.32 (3H, s), 1.98 (3H, s, CH ₃)	—	432(100), 317(31), 234(34), 132(100), 181(50), 117(17), 91(15)
	175—76	2.25 (6H, s, 2CH ₃), 5.02 (Ha), 5.25 (Hb), J (HaHb) 13.0, J _p (Ha) 10.0, J _p (Hb) 12.5, 7.0—7.32 (5H, m, arom), 2.35 (6H, s, CH ₃)	—	—
	148—50	2.24 (6H, s, 2CH ₃), 5.04 (Ha), 5.35 (Hb), J (HaHb) 13.3, J _p (Ha) 9.8, J _p (Hb) 12.8, 7.03—7.35 (5H, m, arom), 2.30 (6H, s, CH ₃)	68.79 (d, J 7.0), 130.42, 137.67, 132.42, 19.20, 148.20 (d, J 6.6), 120.55 (d, J 5.0), 138.26, 133.34, 130.5, 116.9 (d, J 4.5), 19.7, 18.92	—
k	119—20	2.26 (6H, s, 2CH ₃), 5.16(Ha), 5.23 (Hb), J (HaHb) 13.4, J _p (Ha) 9.5, J _p (Hb) 12.9, 6.81—7.25 (5H, m, arom), 2.29 (6H, s, CH ₃)	68.62 (d, J 6.8), 130.24, 137.47, 132.24, 19.17, 149.92 (d, J 6.22), 116.96 (d, J 3.7), 139.42, 126.54, 139.42, 116.96 (d, J 3.75), 20.91, 29.91	—
l	163—64	2.27 (6H, s, 2CH ₃), 5.11 (Ha), 5.29 (Hb), J (HaHb) 13.2, J _p (Ha) 9.6, J _p (Hb) 12.7, 7.03—7.71 (5H, m, arom), 2.35 (3H, s, CH ₃)	68.96 (d, J 7.0), 130.50, 37.88, 132.27, 19.27, 148.60, 122.04 (d, J 4.72), 137.81, 130.59, 129.96, 118.37 (d, J 4.9), 20.13	—
m	179—80	2.25 (s, 2CH ₃), 5.0 (Ha), 6.13 (Hb), J (HaHb) 13.3, J _p (Ha) 11.2, J _p (Hb) 10.9, 7.0—7.54 (5H, m, arom)	69.23 (d, J 6.75), 130.62, 137.98, 132.18, 19.17, 145.01, 125.39, 128.08, 130.43, 130.05, 121.05	372(27), 230(9), 257(9), 181(100), 130(66), 132(44), 147(25), 91(25)
2a	249—50	4.7—5.50 (4H, m, 2CH ₂), 2.27 (6H, s, 2CH ₃), 7.18 (2H, s), 3.1 (8H, s, 4CH ₂)	44.14, 130.65, 137.39, 133.85, 19.24	296(15), 217(50), 132(93), 86(100), 58(27)
b	229—30	—	—	—
c	144—45	5.08—5.45 (4H, m, 2CH ₂), 2.29 (6H, s, 2CH ₃), 7.0—8.0 (8H, m, arom)	—	246(27), 147(67), 130(100), 119(42), 91(34)
d	124—25	4.1 (4H, s, 2CH ₂), 2.20 (s, 2CH ₃), 6.9 (2H, s), 7.18 (4H, s)	36.56, 131.88, 136.28, 132.49, 19.22, 132.13, 131.34, 128.93, 135.04	275(100), 163(53), 121(96), 117(64), 91(30)
e	94—95	4.75—5.60 (4H, m, 2CH ₂), 2.21 (6H, s, 2CH ₃), 6.9—7.22 (7H, m), 2.35 (3H, s, N-CH ₃)	—	—

* All compounds gave satisfactory IR absorptions and elemental analyses.

High resolution MS of 1h: 332.1166(18) C₁₈H₂₁O₄P, 317.0962(4.6) C₁₇H₁₈O₄P, 234.0962(5.9) C₁₈H₁₈, 219.1194 (4.3) C₁₇H₁₅, 147.0414(3.2) C₁₀H₁₁O, 130.0999 (15.3) C₁₀H₁₃, 132.0945(100) C₁₀H₁₂, 117.6723(11.8) C₉H₉, 91.0560